

“THE POLEMIC OF PUBLIC POLICY IMPLEMENTATION IN INDONESIA UNDER JOKO WIDODO GOVERNMENT”

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ABSTRACT

Policies are made to answer the needs of the community, from cities to remote areas. Hopefully, this will be reflected in policymaking in the present and the future. Public policies are governmental decisions and are the result of activities that the government undertakes in pursuance of certain goals and objectives. It can also be said that public policy formulation and implementation involves a well-planned pattern or course of activity. Public policy implementation is an implementation process in terms of realizing public policy goals that have been set by the government. Policy implementation is a practical stage and is distinguished from policy formulation which can be seen as a rhetorical stage. Policy implementation activities will certainly be welcomed with joy by the community if the designation of the policy is truly for the good and has a direct impact on the wider community. During the implementation of public policy, various obstacles will be encountered. To identify the problems with the implementation of Jokowi government public policy (2014-2019) variables from two models Van Meter and Van Horn also Edward III influence the process of implementing public policy. This research is qualitative by using the textual study method by analyzing secondary data from various related literature. From the results of the research, empirical data showed that there are several factors that influence the implementation of public policy in Indonesia. The implementation of public policy found problems due to communication, resources, economics, and social and political conditions.

Keywords: Public Policy, Implementation, Government, Implement Policy Model

1. INTRODUCTION

Public policy is as old as the government. Regardless of the form of ideology, public policies have been formulated and implemented along with the existence of the government. Public policy is defined as the response of a political system through the power of government to the problems of society (Frank Fischer, Gerald J. Miller, Mara S. Sidney, 2007). In other words, public policy is the government's decision to cope with public problems. In another site, the word 'government' defines a person or group of people who are mandated by all members of a political system to make arrangements for the whole system starting from RT, RW, village, district, province, country to supra-state (ASEAN, EU) and the world (WTO, UN). Meanwhile, the 'public' can be society, company, citizen, NGO, and others.

The responsibility of government agencies, both central and regional to formulate, prepare, and implement the public policy. The government is demanded to be able to produce policies that are against conflict or overlap with other regulations that make it ambiguous. However, in reality in the ranking issued by the Worldwide Governance Indicators, the quality of Indonesian policy is low for the Southeast Asia Region, namely 51.9, below the Philippines (55.8), Thailand (59.6), or Malaysia (74.5) (Prawitasari, 2018). This indicates that the resulting policies need improvement in the process, one of which is in terms of policy implementation. The problem that must be overcome by the government is a public problem regarding values or needs, needs, or opportunities that have not been materialized. Although these problems can be identified, they are only possible through public action that is public policy. The characteristics of public problems are interdependent and dynamic. Therefore, a holistic approach is required in order to solve the problem. For this reason, public policy is needed as an instrument to achieve government goals.

According to T. B. Smith, when a policy has been made, it must be implemented and its results must be in accordance with what is expected by the policy makers. The cause of failed policy implementation is because it is not implemented. It happens because it is not in line with the initial plan, or the policymaker does not master the problem. Therefore, the actors involved in implementing the policy must be able to manage coordination in order that they can agree on the policy direction. This is important so that, the implementation can run according to the objectives and be a good policy in the future (Prawitasari, 2018).

In Indonesia, during the administration period of President Joko Widodo (Jokowi) (2014-2019), he issued a number of policies that drew the attention of the public in 2018. Public policy is a step taken by the government to implement the applicable laws and regulations. Through the implementation of policies, the government regulates the running of government. Without policies, the government cannot provide good public services, the government cannot facilitate businesses to grow, and cannot pay taxes properly. The government, led by President Joko Widodo, has been noted to repeatedly change policies in a short time. In fact, the policy was announced to the public but was later canceled. Often,

policies that are certainly drawn up in detail are then changed in a short period of time. One of the examples is an economic policy, which is issued within the first 5 years of the Jokowi administration and considered less successful or problematic when being implemented. In fact, the policy package aims to attract investment and stimulate the business world (Rachman, 2019).

From the discussion above, if one or some of the policies have not achieved its goals without being implemented. However, the implementation requires a very long and complex process. The policy implementation phase will not be started before the goals are determined in advance by the policymakers. Therefore, the policy implementation phase occurs only after laws are enacted and funds are provided to finance the implementation of the policy. However, when a policy is implemented, it does not necessarily mean that it will be properly implemented. There are several obstacles or problems found during the course of the policy. This is what the writer tries to analyze and to identify the dynamics of public policy implementation in the Jokowi era.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW Policy Implementation Model

Regarding the policy product, it ultimately boils down to the level of how to implement the policy and can be actualized. In order to know the substance of policy implementation, the following are some of the models of policy implementation described by experts and observers of public policy, namely:

1. Van Meter and Van Horn models

Implementation of the core policy is an activity to distribute policy output (to deliver policy output) carried out by the implementers to the target group (target group) in an effort to realize the policy objectives. Van Meter and Van Horn (1975) (Winarno, 2013) limit the implementation of policies as actions taken by individuals (or groups) of government or private that are directed to achieve the goals set in previous policy decisions. Policy objectives are expected to emerge when the policy output can be properly received and utilized by the target group, however, in the long term the policy results will be able to be manifested (Dyah Ratih Sulistyastuti, Erwan Agus Purwanto, 2012). The first model is the most classic model introduced by Donald Van Meter and Carl Van Horn (1975). This model confirms that: "Policy implementation runs linearly from public policy, implementers, and public policy

performance." Several variables that influence the public policy process are 1) Implementation activities and communication between organizations, 2) Characteristics and implementing agents/implementers, 3) Economic, social, and political conditions, and 4) The tendency (disposition) of implementing / implementers. The affirmation of the Van Meter and Horn can be illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 1: Model of Policy Implementation according to Meter and Horn

The policy demands the availability of resources, both in the form of funds and other incentives. Policy performance will be low if the funds needed are not sufficiently available. Clarity of standards and targets does not guarantee effective implementation if they are not accompanied by communication between policy implementers in the organization. All policy implementers must understand what is idealized by the policy because what is implemented is the responsibility of the implementer. This problem is also closely related to the characteristics of the implementing bureaucracy. The implementing bureaucracy structure, which has the characteristics, norms, and patterns of relationship, is very influential on the success of policy implementation. Implementing organizations have variables: i) competence and number of staff, ii) range and degree of control, iii) political support, iv) organizational strength, v) degree of openness and freedom of communication, and vi) linkages with policymakers (Kadji, 2015).

All of the above variables shape the attitude of implementers towards the policies they implement, and determine the performance of the policy. The objectivity, neutrality, and cognition of the implementers or policymakers greatly influence their responses to all of these variables. The response of individual implementers or policy implementers is the cause of the success and failure of policy implementation. If the implementer does not understand the policy objectives, especially if the value system that influences his attitude is different from the value system owned by the policymaker, then the policy implementation will not be effective.

2. Model George Edwards III

Implementation of policies is complex and crucial, this is understood because the implementation process involves many people's interactions with interests and at the same time formulates a mechanism for providing information about the policy. Complexity in the implementation process can bring up a number of problems. Edwards III identified four critical factors that affect the success of the implementation process. These four factors are communication, resources, disposition or behavior, and bureaucratic structure (Dyah Ratih Sulistyastuti, Erwan Agus Purwanto, 2012).

Edwards III (1980) stated: "In our approach to the study of policy implementation, we begin in the abstract and ask: What are the preconditions for successful policy implementation? What are the primary obstacles to successful policy implementation? "To answer this important question, Edwards III (1980) offers and considers four factors in implementing public policy, namely:" Communication, resources, dispositions or attitudes, and bureaucratic structure " (Kadji, 2015).

Figure 2: Policy Implementation Model according to Edwards III

In the process of policy implementation, communication plays an important role because implementers must know what they are going to do. Orders to implement the policy must be passed on to the implementer appropriately and consistently. Lack of resources will result in ineffective implementation of policies. Disposition or tendency of the attitude of the executor is defined as the desire and agreement among implementers to implement the policy. If the application of the policy is effectively implemented, then the implementer not only knows what they have to do and has the ability to implement it, but the implementer must also have the desire to implement the policy. Finally, the bureaucratic structure has an impact on application in the sense that the application will not succeed if there are deficiencies in the bureaucratic structure.

a) Communication

In general Edwards III discusses three important things in the communication process policy, namely transmission, consistency, and clarity. The first requirement regarding

transmission in policy communication is those who carry out decisions must know what they must do, policy decisions and orders must be passed on to the right people before policy decisions and orders are followed. Communication must be accurate and must be understood carefully by the implementer. The second is consistency; if policy implementation is to be effective then the order of implementation must be consistent and clear. Furthermore, regarding clarity, if policies are implemented as what is it is expected, then the direction of implementation to the policy implementers is not only accepted but it must also be clear (Winarno, 2013).

b) Resources

The Implementation Order in the policy may be passed clearly and consistently to the implementer, but if the implementer lacks the resources needed to implement policies, implementation tends to be ineffective. Resource is an important factor in the successful implementation of policies. These resources include staff who have good expertise to implement the policy, adequate authority, and facilities to carry out the policy. Staff seeks to be the most important source in implementing policies. A large staff is not necessarily able to implement the policy properly, nor can a small staff. Another important source is authority, which in each authority will be different in every policy. Then about the facilities, an implementer may have adequate staff and may have the authority to carry out their duties, but without an office building for coordination, equipment, and supplies, it is likely being implemented a policy will not be reached (Kadji, 2015).

c) Dispositions

Disposition from policy implementers is an important factor in the implementation of policy. If the implementers have a good attitude toward policy and support a policy, then most likely they implement the policy well. Many policies are implemented well because they have support for implementation, but some policies conflict with the views executor, personal interest, or implementing organization. If the policy is implemented for those who do not support it, then mistakes cannot be avoided, namely the gap between policy decisions and policy achievement (Winarno, 2013).

d) Bureaucratic Structure

Bureaucracy is one of the organizations that is most often implementing a policy. Bureaucracy has a structure made to find solutions to every problem in society. There are two main characteristics of bureaucracy, namely the work procedures of basic measurements often called SOPs, and fragmentation. SOPs develop as an internal response to the limited time and resources of implementers and the desire for uniformity in work. Fragmentation comes from pressures outside the bureaucracy, such as the legislature, interest groups, and the nature of policies that influence the nature of government bureaucratic policies (Winarno, 2013).

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted with a qualitative approach, namely by focusing on the general principles of fundamental social phenomena in society. Therefore the object of analysis in a qualitative approach is the meaning of social and cultural phenomena by using the culture of the community concerned to get an overview of certain categorizations (Bungin, 2001). The research approach used is a descriptive qualitative approach. By using the library research method, this data collection method is a technique of collecting secondary data where the data obtained are taken, analyzed, and quoted from various sources. Secondary data is data obtained not directly from the source of literature that supports the proposal. This study uses secondary data, through scientific books or research results, documents, journals, articles, newspapers, and other documents relevant to this research.

4. DISCUSSION

Definition of Public Policy Implementation

According to Webster's Dictionary, the word to implement comes from the Latin "implementum" from the origin of the words "impere" and "plere". The word "implore" is meant "to fill up", or "to fill in", which means to fill fully; complete, while "plere" means "to fill", filling. If the definition of implementation above is put together with public policy, then the word implementation of public policy can be interpreted as the activity of completion or implementation of a public policy that has been established/ approved by the use of means (tools) to achieve policy objectives. However, in the public policy process, policy implementation is a practical stage and is distinguished from policy formulation which can be seen as a rhetorical stage.

Public policy implementation is an implementation process in terms of realizing public policy goals that have been set by the government. But before a policy is implemented or realized, then we will first know or explore how public policy before implemented. Public policy, seen from the instrumental perspective, is a tool to achieve a goal related to the government's efforts to realize public values. Public values as a policy objective can take various forms. But in general, public policy is a tool to: (i) realize idealized values of society such as justice, equality, and openness. (ii) solve problems faced by the community for example; problems of poverty, crime, and poor public services. (iii) take advantage of new opportunities for a better life for the community such as encouraging investment, service innovation, and increasing exports. (iv) protect the public from harmful private practices such as making consumer protection laws, practice licenses, and interference permits (Winarno, 2007).

Policy implementation is the stage of decision-making, as are the articles of a legislative law, the issuance of an executive regulation, and the issuance of court decisions, or the issuance of regulatory standards and the consequences of policies for society that affect several aspects of their lives. Although a policy is taken appropriately, the possibility of failure can still occur if the implementation process is not right. Even a policy that is reliable even if it is implemented poorly and optimally, then the policy fails to achieve the goals set by the makers. The actual policy implementation is not only related to the mechanism of elaborating political decisions into routine procedures through bureaucratic channels, but more than that, it involves the problem of conflict, decisions, and who gets what from a policy. Therefore, it is not wrong to say that policy implementation is an important aspect or dimension of the entire policy process. The whole process of setting a new policy can be started or implemented if the goals and objectives that were originally general are detailed; a program has been designed and a number of funds have been allocated to realize these objectives. The effectiveness of the implementation of this policy is strongly influenced by the behavior of its implementers and the environment that influences each other so that policy implementation is a dialectical process where the objective and subjective dimensions of policy formulation cannot be separated from its empirical practice (Kadji, 2015).

From the description above, an illustration is obtained that public policy implementation is a process of administrative activities carried out after the policy is established/approved. This activity is located between policy formulation and policy evaluation. Policy implementation contains top-down logic, which means reducing/interpreting alternatives that are still abstract or macro into concrete or micro alternatives. In other site, policy formulation contains bottom-up logic, in the sense that this process begins with mapping public needs or accommodating environmental demands followed by the search and selection of alternative solutions, and then it is proposed to be determined.

The Concept of Public Policy Implementation

The implementation of public policy is one of the dimensions in the public policy process, which also determines whether a policy is in contact with interests and can be accepted by the public. In this case, it can be emphasized that it can be done in the planning stage or formulation of policy formulation as well as possible, but if at the implementation stage the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are not considered, then what is expected from a policy product? Finally, it is ensured at the policy evaluation stage, it will produce an assessment that the formulation and implementation of the policy are not in line; that the implementation of the policy was not as expected; even making the policy product becomes a stumbling block for policymakers themselves (Suharno, 2010).

In the dimension of public policy implementation, an in-depth understanding of the study of public policy is needed, which in scientific development will at least lead to two main

perspectives, i) Political Perspective, and ii) Perspective of Public Administration. First; the political perspective, that public policy in the dimensions of formulation, implementation, and evaluation of policies in a series of processes, is ensured to be at the level of differences debates, and conflicts of interest between the stakeholders of public policy (the government also includes the legislative, private and public), which results in postponement of discussion and establishing a public policy. For example, in the discussion on Regional Regulations on Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD), do we not see the process from the stage of discussion of program activities and budgets, until the stipulation of the Regulation, sometimes between the executive and legislative branches in the regions have a nerve war, and finally the Governor must intervene to reconcile the dispute between the Mayor / Regent and the local People Representative Council (DPRD). Second; from the perspective of public administration, public policy is certain to be in contact with SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures), which are guidelines for the flow and work system of each policy product that will be implemented including talking about the capacity of leaders and implementers of public policy, therefore the vision, mission and grand strategy that has been determined can be manifested in a realistic, directed and concrete action and can be accountable to the public (Winarno, 2007).

The importance of the implementation dimension of a policy, the main requirements that must be considered are: i) those who will implement a decision should know what they are doing, ii) policy decisions and implementation regulations, must be transmitted to the appropriate personnel according to the goals and direction of the policy, iii) if the policy must be appropriately implemented, then the policy product is not just acceptable but it is clear what is the target and direction of the policy. These requirements must be fulfilled cause consequences following i) the implementers will be confused about what they should do, ii) they will have their own discretion (authority) in accordance with their wishes to encourage the successful implementation of the policy, and iii) policy implementers will differ in their views from leaders in terms of the implementation or implementation of a policy, and finally will have an impact on the failure of policy implementation (Winarno, *Kebijakan Publik: Teori, Proses dan Studi Kasus*, 2013).

The implementation of the policy is actions taken by individuals (or groups) of government and private sector directed to achieve the goals set in previous policy decisions. These actions include efforts to change decisions into operational technical measures within a certain period of time as well as in the context of continuing efforts to achieve major and minor changes determined by policy decisions. What needs to be emphasized here is that the policy implementation phase will not begin before the goals and objectives are set or identified by policy decisions. Then, the implementation phase occurs only after laws are enacted and funds and other resources are made available to finance the implementation of the policy.

The Dynamics of Public Policy Implementation in Indonesia

a. The Troubled Public Policy Package in Joko Widodo Government

During this period time, the Jokowi administration in 2014-2019 issued several public policies. However, when the policy is being implemented having problems, fails, or is less successful, even if it is only an announcement, but it has not been implemented yet. In other words, if the application is canceled, this policy is considered inconsistent.

1. Public Policy 16 Economic Package

There were 16 economic policy packages issued in the first 5 years of the Jokowi administration in 2014-2019 considered to be less successful. In fact, the policy package aims to attract investment and advance the business world. Sarman Simanjorang, Chairperson of the Jakarta Indigenous Indonesian Entrepreneurs Association (HIPPI), also said that current policies must be thoroughly evaluated. However, implementation in the second period of Jokowi's government can be even better. The 16 economic policy packages issued by the government were not comprehensively evaluated. Sarman continued, that most of these policies only ended on paper. Implementation in the field is not appropriate and some even do not work at all. Then, what is expected by President Jokowi is only as a policy on paper, but in the field implementation it is not in line with and not felt by the business world (Yuniar, 2019).

2. Public Policy on the Application of Biodiesel B20

The B20 Biodiesel Application Policy has been in the public spotlight, namely mixing diesel with Crude Palm Oil (CPO). This policy led to contradictions among others from the Land Transport Organization (Organda) and the Indonesian Truck Employers Association (Aprindo) which felt the direct impact of the policy. Aprindo's Deputy Chairperson explained that truck vehicles will need a water separator to be able to consume this B20 diesel fuel, while most trucks do not yet have such a device (Prawitasari, 2018).

3. Public Policy on the Price of Fuels (BBM).

The Indonesian government had issued a policy on fuel prices that were hasty or wishy-washy and were later canceled. This policy also shook the news by canceling the increase in the price of premium fuel oil (BBM) in just one hour. In the middle of a series of IMF-World Bank meetings in Bali, the government in this case the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, represented by the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources Ignasius Jonan announced the increase in premium fuel prices. Shortly afterward, information emerged that the decision was postponed while awaiting the readiness of PT Pertamina as a state-owned enterprise (BUMN) that has responsibilities related to fuel. This is in accordance with the direction of the President's plan to increase the price of Premium in Java, Madura, and Bali (Jamali) to Rp 7,000 and outside of Jamali to Rp 6,900 (Rachman, 2019).

4. Public Policy on the Increase in Toll Road Rates

The latest policy is the application of Prof. toll road tariff adjustments. Dr. Ir. Sedyatmo. The toll that is used to go to Sukarno-Hatta Airport (Soetta). In fact, the tariff will rise on Thursday, February 14, 2019, but was canceled within the previous day. Previously, a policy change in a short period of time had also occurred during the implementation of the Jakarta Outer Ring Road (JORR) toll transaction system integration. The implementation of the toll transaction system integration was even delayed several times. Toll transaction system integration is a simplification of transactions on a number of toll roads. With integration, toll road users only need to make a one-time transaction, then the applicable tariff is a single tariff according to vehicle class without calculating mileage. The integration that was originally going to be implemented on June 13, 2018 (announced June 12, 2018) was postponed to June 20, 2018. However, the planned implementation on June 20 was finally postponed (Rachman, 2019).

b. Factors Affecting Public Policy

Many factors cause or influence public policy products when they are implemented. There are two public policy implementation models put forward by experts namely Donald Van Meter and Van Horn, and Edward III. The intent of the two models is less the same. According to Van Meter and Horn, there are four variables that influence the process of implementing public policy: Implementation activities and communication between organizations; Characteristics and implementing agents/implementers; Economic, social, and political conditions; and the disposition of the executor/implementer (Winarno, *Kebijakan Publik: Teori, Proses dan Studi Kasus*, 2013). The Edward III model proposes 4 (four) variables that greatly affect the success of policy implementation, namely:

Figure 3: Edward III Public Implementation Model

Communication (communication); communication is a means to disseminate information, both from the top down and from the bottom up. To avoid the distortion of

information conveyed by superiors to subordinates, the need for timeliness in the delivery of information, information must be clear and requires accuracy and consistency in conveying information. Resources (sources), the sources in implementing the policy play an important role, because the implementation of the policy will not be effective if the supporting resources are not available. These sources include:

1. Relatively few staff have the expertise and skills to implement the policy.
2. Information that is adequate or relevant for implementation purposes
3. Support from the environment to successfully implement the policy
4. Authority of the implementer to implement the policy.

Disposition or Attitude; relating to how the implementer's attitude in supporting a policy implementation. Often the implementers are willing to take the initiative in order to achieve the policy, depending on the extent of the authority they have. **Bureaucratic** structure (bureaucratic structure); a policy often involves several institutions or organizations in the implementation process, so effective coordination between related institutions is needed to support the successful implementation.

However, to identify the problems with the implementation of Jokowi government public policy (2014-2019) not all variables of the two models are found in the dynamics of public policy implementation. But it is adjusted to the problem factor that lies behind the implementation of the policy.

c. Identification of Public Policy Issues

☐ 16 Policy 16 Economic Package

There are two crucial problems faced during the implementation of the 16 Economic Package policies, namely the discrepancy between the Central and Regional Governments and the World Economy being Unfriendly (Yuniar, 2019). The first problem identification is the uncertainty between the two actors due to communication factors. According to Edwards III one of the variables that influence the process of implementing public policy is communication. The communication factor is often seen as complicated, which has the potential for communication distortion. Communication is a means to disseminate information, both from the top (central government) to the bottom (local government) and from the bottom up. In public organizations, organizational leaders or superiors should be able to communicate policies and create working conditions for staff or implementers to have the capacity and motivation to work as desired by public policy itself. This must be considered by the central government and regional governments must synergize with each other with good communication, therefore the policy products issued do not overlap with local regulations. The communication between the two actors is to avoid misunderstanding/information communication delivered. There are still mismatches between the policies of the central government and regional governments, especially in the licensing

and investment processes. Businessmen and investors often experience confusion when they have obtained the blessing of the central government but are hindered by regional policies. There have been a number of cases where investors have received approval from the provincial government but when they arrived in the area there were more obstacles. In other site, there is a governor in the district who also has the same authority and they can also hinder and do not give permission. This is one of the policies packages but implementation in the field is not working.

The identification of the second problem, namely the unfriendly world economy, is related to the opinion of Van Meter and Van Horn. One of the variables that influence the process of implementing public policy is economic, social and political conditions. This problem comes from the world economic environment which also influences the domestic economic atmosphere which of course also impacts on the implementation of our economic policies. President Joko Widodo said that at this time the world economy was not friendly. Some countries in the world are experiencing economic decline and even some are experiencing a recession. This was stated at the Conference of Engineer Organizations in ASEAN. The world economy is currently not friendly. Some countries experience economic setbacks. Some countries even began experiencing an economic recession. By seeing this condition, countries in ASEAN must be able to fortify themselves from all possibilities that can shake the economy to keep growing stable and sustainable (Yuniar, 2019). Try to take advantage of setbacks in some areas as an opportunity for us to jump forward. To anticipate this, all ASEAN countries have developed new innovations and breakthroughs, to be able to take advantage of the currently difficult world economic opportunities. By taking advantage of opportunities in the current difficult world economic situation, it will become an opportunity for us in ASEAN to develop faster.

☐ Biodiesel Policy

From the reality of policy implementation, the problem that often arises when policy implementation is the absence of socialization by the government. This also happened to the Biodiesel policy, seems the government made a decision by implementing the policy of one party. Even though, the government should not need to rush to implement a public policy. Field trials are essential, for example, the sampling taken must also be carefully determined, paying attention to the media used, the area, and the distance. Therefore, the policies made are truly policies that are solutions to the problems needed and expected by the community. The government should coordinate with the people who directly feel the policy, such as the Land Transportation Organization (Organda) and the Indonesian Truck Employers Association (Aptrindo). Suitability of raw materials (diesel oil with Crude Palm Oil) and the availability of tools or media to consume these materials were important to note. In addition, the price of CPO which is in the range of Rp 8,000 to Rp 9,000 is feared to add to the burden of state subsidies if it is mixed with solar subsidies which are only Rp 5,150. Then, will have an impact on the government because of the burden of the subsidies (Prawitasari, 2018).

If drawn further, an implementation that is prone to contradictions like this can be avoided if the manufacturing process involves a policy analyst. Policy analysts act as policy prompters every time the government makes a policy decision, regarding it is a policy that regulates social, economic, religious, and cultural issues in society. A policy analyst must be able to play a role by offering alternative policy choices to stakeholders. The alternative policy choices offered must be based on scientific studies and supporting data in the field. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct a field trial by consider into account the area, distance, raw materials, and media used.

Identification of problems in Biodiesel policy is at the resource level. According to Edward III, one of the variables that influence the process of implementing public policy is resources. In terms of human resources, the main weakness is related to professionalism, competence, and ethics. One of the points in the resource is a relatively large number of expert staff and has the expertise and skills to implement the policy. The staff in question are experts who have the skills and competence and professionalism for the policy making process. In other words, we need a policy analyst. However, unfortunately, the number of policy analysts in Indonesia is still very small when compared to the number of policies produced by the government. Data from the LAN Center for Policy Analysis (Pusaka), until September 2018 there were only 172 policy analysts in Indonesia. This number is certainly very small considering that the distribution of policy analysts is not uneven throughout Indonesia. Not all provinces in Indonesia have a policy analyst. For example, in Kalimantan, of five provinces only two have policy analysts, namely Central Kalimantan and West Kalimantan (Prawitasari, 2018). Even more astonishing, it turns out that of the two policy analysts, no one has received policy analyst training. Especially the training was conducted by LAN as a policy analyst advisory agency.

☐ Fuel Price Increase Policy

The identification of problems in the fuel increase policy is the communication level. According to Edward III, one of the variables that influence the process of implementing public policy is communication. The community is taught to be patient and not in a hurry to respond to policies issued. Policies in the Jokowi era were inconsistent, many policies quickly changed only in a short time. The main problem is that communication must be two-way. From the side of community policy then taught by the government of Jokowi, if there is a policy told to be patient first, do not rush to respond. This is because suddenly the policy can be revoked again. That was the impact of the problem of public policy communication in the Jokowi era (Rini, 2018).

This policy was issued and highlighted the news by canceling the increase in the price of premium fuel oil (BBM) in just one hour. The government changed the status of Premium Fuel Oil in Java, Madura, and Bali (Jamali) into assignments in 2018. The Presidential Regulation (Perpres) as a legal umbrella that had been previously drafted was finally revised. President

Jokowi on May 24, 2018, signed Perpres Number 43 of 2018 concerning Amendment to Presidential Regulation Number 191 of 2014 concerning the Supply, Distribution, and Selling Prices of Retail Fuel Oil. In Presidential Decree No. 43 of 2018 it was confirmed, that the minimum RON gasoline type 88 (Premium) fuel must be available at the gas stations in the Jamali region. In fact, the government had previously revoked the status of Pertamina assignment to provide Premium type of fuel in Jamali. However, then the government re-assigned the government to be able to provide Premium BBM in all regions, including Jamali. With this Perpres, even though Jamali is not included in the Assignment Area, Jamali can still get a premium allocation with an assignment status provided that it is approved by the results of a joint meeting with the Coordinating Minister for Economic Affairs and approved by the relevant Ministers (Rachman, 2019).

◎ Toll Road Rate Increase Policy

In 2019, the policy regarding tariff increases for several Toll Roads will be issued and each has its own announcement or socialization schedule. Toll Road of Prof. Dr. Ir. Soedijatmo, the Jakarta-Tangerang and Tangerang-Merak Toll Road and others that were socialized in 2019. For Toll Road Soedijatmo announcement is scheduled for February 2019 and the socialization has started well through the media, releases, and banners have all been done even though it has not been optimal. It is just that the implementation of this policy is still delayed within a certain period. In fact, Jasa Marga who announced this decision had received a Decree from the Minister of Public Works Number 121 / KPTS / M / 2019 dated February 6, 2019 regarding the toll tariff adjustment. In order to provide more optimal socialization to the public, especially toll road users, adjusting tariffs on Toll Road Dr. Ir. Soedijatmo was postponed until the time to be informed later (Rachman, 2019).

Corporate Secretary of PT Jasa Marga (Persero) Tbk, Agus Setiawan at the time explained this delay was based on an order from the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing (PUPR). PT Jasa Marga received an instruction from the Ministry of PUPR that the implementation was postponed. This delay is considered approaching the Eid Mubarak or Lebaran holiday. However, until now the Minister of Public Works and Public Housing (PUPR) has not yet socialized the details of the price increase. The socialization of the details of the toll tariff has become a polemic because the increase in a number of toll road tariffs has long been realized. After the socialization, the tariff increase should have been immediately applied (Rachman, 2019).

Identification of the problems in the Toll Road Tariff Increase policy is at the level of the economic, social, political environment. According to Van Meter and Van Horn, one of the variables that influence the process of implementing public policy is economic, social and political conditions. Problems with the policy of increasing toll road tariffs occur at the social and political levels. In the social sphere, the delay in the implementation of the tariff increase is due to the approach to leave during the Eid Mubarak holidays. Therefore, attention was

first directed to the success of the homecoming flow, with the consideration that the condition of the Jabodetabek residents is still a lot outside the city and the concentration of Lebaran. Meanwhile, for the political sphere, quoted from CNBC Indonesia, apparently the new toll tariff increase will be announced after the inauguration of the President and Vice President for the 2019-2024 period. The inauguration of the President and Vice President 2019-2024 itself is planned to take place on Sunday, October 20, 2019 (Rachman, 2019).

5. CONCLUSION

Policy implementation is one of the most important aspects of the entire policy process. It is often argued that the majority of problems in the policy process are the matter of implementing faulty policies, which are the duties and responsibilities of the executive. The policy implementation process can increase in terms of; serious implementers working on a systematic path. There are always methods and ways to meet challenges and sort out problems. If we find ambiguity in several things, then what needs to be done is to find out by conducting a direct sampling of the issues that will be made into policy.

On other site, it can also be said that a well-implemented public policy is a form of intervention carried out continuously by the government in the public interest, while at the same time encouraging public participation in broad development. Strictly speaking, the aspects of policy implementation need to be understood and examined: i) what is appropriate and feasible to do and what does not need to be done by the government and implementer in the stages of policy implementation, ii) what causes or influences it, and iii) what are the impacts and added values of public policy if implemented or not implemented.

There are at least two suggestions that can be given to improve the quality of the resulting policy implementation. First, strengthening human resources; human resources who are implementing the policy must have the ability to master the policies that will be offered to the community. People are not confused and can understand the new policies that will be implemented, then disappointment does not arise in the future. Second, strengthening the objectives of policy-making; when a policy is prepared, there can be actors who have goals, both in the interests of the group and personal interests. Therefore, a conflict of interest occurred, and finally, the policy made was not for the benefit of the wider community, but only for certain circles. It is important to ensure that the policy is aligned with community needs.

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